

**APPLICABILITY OF RETROSPECTIVE EXPERIENTIAL
LEARNING TO COUNTER SOCIAL EXCLUSION, TO FOSTER
SOCIAL CAPITAL AND ECLECTIC THEORIES OF
ECONOMICS**

BY

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the thesis entitled “APPLICABILITY OF RETROSPECTIVE EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING TO COUNTER SOCIAL EXCLUSION, TO FOSTER SOCIAL CAPITAL AND ECLECTIC THEORIES OF ECONOMICS ” is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, it contains no material previously published or written by another person nor material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma of the university or other institute of higher learning, except where due acknowledgement has been made in the text.

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ABSTRACT

APPLICABILITY OF RETROSPECTIVE EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING TO COUNTER SOCIAL EXCLUSION, TO FOSTER SOCIAL CAPITAL AND ECLECTIC THEORIES OF ECONOMICS

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the relationship between REL and tourist grievances.
- The study is basically a fact finding one that concentrates on improving the service quality and to understand the effect of REL experiment on behavioural science knowledge and to understand whether local tourist guides have a positive outlook towards their jobs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is explorative in nature and hence is designed as a hypothesis testing one. Two kinds of hypothesis testing designs are introduced.

Before-and-after without control design: In this design a single test group is selected and the dependent variable is measured before the introduction of Retrospective Experiential Learning (REL). The REL programme is then introduced and the dependent variable is measured again after the REL programme has been introduced. The effect of the treatment would be equal to the level of phenomenon after the REL programme minus the level of phenomenon before the REL programme.

Before-and-after with control design: In this design two groups are selected and the dependent variable is measured in both the groups for an identical time period before the

introduction of REL. The REL programme is then introduced into the test group only, and the dependent variable is measured in both for an identical time-period after the introduction of the REL. The REL effect is determined by subtracting the change in the dependent variable in the control group from the change in the dependent variable in test group.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

One of the main methods to distinguish an eco-tourism endpoint is to provide reliably great excellence facility than other kinds of tourism. The main factor is to come across or outdo the target travellers' service excellence outlooks. Consumer gratification is one of the central drives of an excellence organisation scheme. This brain storming session was aimed at improving the tourist satisfaction and the tourist guides' motivation levels. Client devotion can be continued only by upholding a positive assessment when equated with other players. According to REL discussions tourist's expectations are formed by their past experiences, mouth publicity, and destination advertising through websites. The tourists choose destinations on these bases and, after receiving service, compare the perceived service with the expected service. The coming deliberations may be directed towards enlightening the service excellence. As the local tourist guides belong to local people, their social status needs to be improved. Therefore, eco-tourism has to be promoted based on inclusive growth. Social upliftment of the tribal populace has to be given the paramount importance, as they are still the marginalised sector in terms of living standards. Local tourist guides are tribes. They belong to the marginalised category. Basically, it's an experimental design. Before after the same group undergoing intervention, resulting in social acceptance after the application of REL. Improved guiding and better economic benefits help them to be part of main stream and effectively counter social exclusion.

Positive vibes always contribute to better customer satisfaction. Here in this study REL and Survey feedback interventions resulted in a better attitude towards the behaviour

model. As it has produced better results in destinations like Thenmala and PTR, it's high time to take it to other ecotourism destinations across the globe which requires consultancy services as well as manpower supports. Internationalisation of ecotourism operations through better services can bring benefits to ecotourism operators at home and its foreign counterparts. As ecotourism follows stringent quality parameters, development potential is limited in particular destinations, the next option is to move it across the globe so that the business potential keeps on growing. As the emphasis is on intergroup and intragroup dynamics with the assistance of structured activities like Retrospective Experiential Learning it results in better interrelations and social capital.

CHAPTER-1: CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK FOR THE STUDY, EMERGING FROM THE SURVEY OF LITERATURE

1.1 Significance of Retrospective Experiential Learning , Eco-tourism and Eclectic Theories of Economics

Eco-tourism is a relatively new concept. People who are concerned with tourism industry have to be rigorously trained in order to understand the new concepts, applications, methodologies etc. Eco-tourism intermediaries like forest officials, local guides and ministerial staff for eco-tourism projects come under this purview. Retrospective Experiential Learning Principles are the most effective tools to implement training methodologies in eco- tourism.

REL is a relatively permanent change in behaviour that occurs as a result of reproducing one's best previous experiences. Here the experiment has been done at Thenmala and PTR regarding Customer Relations Management. Guides have been asked to recollect their experiences about the following. Left a tourist in a good frame of mind or explained something to the tourist in a way that he or she understood and the guide learned something unexpectedly. The chances are that the guides are aware of some of the elements of their strategies but equally the chances are that there are some crucial bits of which the guides have no conscious knowledge. Guides have been asked to recollect their words and style of communication such as gestures, postures, composure, disposition, overall body language and eye contact and ultimately approach at that point of time. They have been asked to document it and go through it. The idea was to make it standardised rather than happening it erratically. Objective of this experiment was to help one live within one's potential rather than imposing a strategy from outside. Retrospective Experiential Learning (REL) is a learning instrument developed by the researcher.

Kerala tourism is a role model for manpower development and improved service quality. It can develop its resources across the globe by providing consultancy services to other eco-tourism destinations like Kenya, Zambia, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania by ensuring the triple bottom lines of eclectic theories of economics viz. ownership, location, and internationalization. Uniqueness and vibrancy of Kerala ecotourism can be taken to international levels by focusing on service quality through better application of behaviour science with greater emphasis on the developed learning theory Retrospective Experiential Learning.

1.2 Need and Importance of the Study

Kerala, 'God's Own Country', was formed as a state in the Indian union in 1956. Since then its progress in various fields has been remarkable. With 38863 Sq.kms of land area, it now accommodates nearly 32 million people. It has a peculiar pattern of development known as 'Kerala model of development' (Mathew, 2005)[1]. But another study says "the basic characteristic of Kerala model of development is the paradox of social development and economic stagnation" (George, 1993)[2]. There are spectacular improvements in the quality of life; there is 100% literacy, low infant mortality, high life expectancy, favourable sex ratio in favour of women and minimum rural-urban differences. In spite of all the shortfalls outlined above, tourism in Kerala has recorded remarkable growth in recent years. International tourist arrivals increased to 3.46 lakhs in 2015 from 2.08 lakhs in 2010. Domestic tourist arrivals (excluding pilgrims) rose from 52.40 lakhs in 2010 to 59.46 lakhs in 2015. Thus in five years to 2015, annual growth rate for foreign and domestic tourist arrivals are respectively 13.27% and 2.69%. (The Economic Review, 2016) [3] According to the study of

World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) on tourism sector in the State, Travel and Tourism generates as much as 7.7% of GSP and 6.2% of total employment. Visitor exports (tourism exports) are worked out as 14.3% of the total export of the State (World Travel and Tourism Council, 2016)[4].

It is an unquestionable fact that the State generates revenue and a lot of employment is created in tourism field. But the conservation of the ecology and environment is also equally important. So such a study draws in-depth importance.

The govt launched 'ECO- Star', ("Going Eco", 2006) [5] which will award points to tourism ventures for their contribution to the environment and people of the area in which they are established.

ECO stands for Environment and Community –Oriented. The ECO – Star system will award points to tourism ventures in the state –resorts, hotels, tour operators, and transport for adopting certain ECO-measures.

Initiative in the following areas will carry maximum points.

- Picking at least 60 percent of the labour force from the local community
- The use of local resources in the day to day functioning so as to enhance the purchasing power of the local community.
- The use of low emission alternate means of transport
- Promotion of traditional arts and crafts
- Initiatives to protect endangered flora and fauna
- Rerouting a percentage of the profits back to the community to set up schools, dispensaries, garbage plants and introduction of energy-efficient technologies.

Since the popularity of responsible travel is rising, such a classification is inevitable. A responsible traveller seeks to enrich both his experience and the destination he visits. **In Kerala Eco-tourism has been implemented only in selected**

forest destinations and for this study Thenmala and Periyar Tiger Reserve (PTR) have been selected.

The data show that in the opinion of the respondents, the situation regarding the person based factors of performance is far from satisfactory. *Organisational wide HRD programmes with a special emphasis on behavioural science training programmes, as required to rectify the situation by reducing deficiencies and by replacing them with corresponding developments alone can improve the situation.*

1.3 Survey of Literature

A substantial volume of literature both at macro and micro levels can be seen on the subject of tourism and its impacts. A thorough literature survey has been conducted, especially in the context of Kerala for constructing a theoretical framework for this study. The literature survey had helped to understand and appreciate the earlier studies conducted in the field of tourism and it provided a broad framework for this study.

The paper in the Journal of Workplace Learning by Olsson, Bjoorn & Jonson, 2008) [6], speaks on retrospective learning about insensible, budding wisdom amongst workers of an establishment and proposes in what way to understand these instants of empirical wisdom for organisational wisdom. This published research work put on the applied study, converging on the empirical wisdom coming through routine activities in the experimental establishment at Volvo Car's manufacture unit based in Sweden. The research proposes that the capability development that happened earlier should develop an essential portion of upcoming instructive procedures. This research is an advancement of the abovementioned one, as the quoted one focuses on actual structural instruction procedures. In the meanwhile, the investigator steered this test for enhancing

structural efficiency by focussing on the three-way extremity lines - better client satisfaction, greater financial welfares for workforces and ability enrichment for workforces on customary basis

In a journal article by Beerli & Martin, 2004 [7], a considerable dimension of research has been enclosed concerning the issues impelling a destination's brand equity. Nevertheless, some proportions concerning service excellence have been enclosed, the paper which was available in Annals of Tourism does not stretch a detailed examination in connection with visitor dealings managing. Here the investigator distillates on refining visitor dealings managing through performance reform. The research paper published by Chowdhary & Prakash, in 2008 [8], portrays a respectable proportional reading amongst outing attendant training and additional packages in connection with approach and method. In this research, the investigator focuses on necessity based traveller guide training and its progressive influences.

Seven Strategies for Change' has been suggested for change agents (Kotter & Schlesinger, 1979)[9] The said article in Harvard Business Review is concerned about choosing a strategy for change. Here the researcher has applied Survey Feedback in addition to the seven strategies.

In another paper published in Personnel Psychology (Fedor, D. B. et al. 2006) [10] pronounces around forming a constructive viewpoint from the part of workers throughout the transformation procedure. Now in this investigational research, emphasis has been agreed on collaborative management during the REL procedure. Empowerment of service workers have been covered in detail (Bowen, D. E. et al, 1992) [11] and it says about legendary stories of employees who recovered failed business transactions. Here, the researcher has applied Survey Feedback to understand

the reasons for ineffective service recovery. The article in American Sociological Review on the empowerment of service workers emphasize on the approach of frontline interaction personnel.

This study has undertaken an effort to understand the relationship between REL and tourist grievances (Mathew Renganathan & Joseph, 2012) [12].

In this study, interventions are structured activities that help small teams to sort out the intergroup or intragroup problems within the organisation. Retrospective Experiential Learning is a behaviour science intervention designed by the investigator intended to improve the day to day guiding activities in ecotourism destinations. Ultimately it results in greater teamwork, greater team cohesiveness and ultimately results in better team building to improve the social capital. Ecotourism destinations are unique in their natural beauty, Better guest relation management and better teamwork among local tourist guides make the ecotourism products in Kerala unique and appealing. A good business model is replicable all over the world. Through better guiding, the improved service can be provided by the ecotourism directorate in other parts of the world like Kenya, Zambia, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania, etc. Ultimately it will boost up the eclectic theories of economics by concentrating on the baselines of Eclectic Theories like making the business international through consultancy ownership and customising the product for the locational needs.

In the article published by Yagil D. in 2002 [13], the practical difficulty in monitoring frontline employees is elaborated and it says that employees operate in their way. As it is a practical problem, the researcher had developed a new learning theory that helps employees to work within the peripherals of their potential. In another scholarly article by Bradley & Sparks, 2000) [14], the positive correlation between employee empowerment and customer satisfaction is elaborated. Hereafter a series of

interventions using REL and survey feedback and after the application of the new learning theory customer complaints wrinkled considerably. Here the findings of the research findings corroborate the findings of the said research article published in the Journal of Applied Social Psychology.

The journal article (Akst, 2007) [15], which was published in the Wall Street Journal says about the relationship between motivational performance and considerate leadership. In this study, motivational performance score has been taken two times and it has been found that once the organisation has been exposed to a culture of openness and trust Motivational Performance Score (MPS) has been improved.

The exploration learning that is available in American Social Review (Balu, 1970) [16] speaks about businesses that stay to gratify its clients reinforce its source base. Now the scholar had done REL as a learning intervention for measuring the tourist contentment levels. Afterward the application of REL, sightseers articulated better fulfilment. Contented sightseers are probable to be recurring guests of the place.

The article (Friendlander & Pickle, 1968) [17] says about an organisation that uses scarce resources that are available in its environment has got greater control over its environment. In eco-tourism destinations, destinations the tribal tourist guides who are known as the sons of the land, explore the undiscovered nooks and corners of the dense forest and let the tourist see uncharted places.

The article in Sloan Management Review (Pearce, 1982) [18] says about using the company mission as a strategic tool. Here the researcher had used the exploratory study as regards with REL Strategy formulation and problem identification was done with mission and vision statements of the eco-tourism destinations.

The article in California Management Review (Miles & Snow, 1992) [19] says about the reasons for failures in network organisations. The main reason is their inability to standardised products and services. Twelve eco-tourism destinations are at operational level. But there is no consistency as far as the operations are considered. So, the researcher had taken two destinations which are at two extremes of Kerala and tried to address their problems from the same perspective.

The research article (Clifford, 2000) [20] says about the problems created by decentralising innovation at the subsidiary level. In this experimental study, the tourist guides under the guidance of the researcher developed a tool that helped them to optimise their potential and apply in day to day guiding.

The research article (Arnst, Crockett, Reinhardt & Shinai, 2000) [21] says about doing innovations at different centres quite distinguishable from one another. As eco-tourism from the State is being promoted as a unique product, distinguishable innovations regarding adventure sports and ethnic chores have been brainstormed with the support of local tourist guides.

The research article (Jaffe, 2006) [22] says about the importance of keeping secrets in the organisation. The same concept has been used in this research writing for maintaining the uniqueness of the guiding operations. In simple terms, it can be rated as making the accidental good exposures part of the day to day operations.

CHAPTER 2: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Statement of the Problem

The National Geographic Traveller has found Kerala as ‘one of the ten paradises’ and one of the 50 places in the world recommended to be visited in a life time. The Government of Kerala is trying to develop tourism in Kerala, because it is conceived as an instrument for social and economic growth. There is tremendous growth in the number of foreign tourist arrivals, domestic tourist arrivals, and tourism earnings, employment generated by tourism and also in the outlay of the government regarding tourism. In this connection it has been found that a study about the ecological aspects of tourism and making the concerned people aware and get them trained is a necessity. Researcher had a strong felt concern towards the economic, social and cultural status of the local guides. Is it possible to improve the guest relations management in Eco-tourism through the application of REL? Is it possible to improve the behaviour science knowledge of local people who are involved in Eco-tourism through the application of REL These are some of the questions that are to be answered.

2.2 Scope and Coverage

Though the whole Kerala is blessed with unmatched natural diversity that provides immense scope for eco-tourism, there are certain areas or destinations which are already developed as far as eco-tourism is concerned. Development of tourism in these areas has a wide variety of impacts on the ecology of that locality and on the overall contribution towards tourism in the state. Naturally development of certain areas would help similar areas or destinations to develop their tourism potential in eco-friendly way. The impact of the tourism development is directly felt by the people who are directly or indirectly involved in tourism business. Therefore the universe of

the present study is limited to those areas where eco-tourism is developed and to those persons who are directly connected with eco-tourism business. This study is explorative in nature as a hypothesis testing experimental one and the first of its kind in Kerala. Therefore the study has been conducted mainly to explore the positive impacts of Organisation Development in the eco-tourism developed areas. Eventhough there are 56 locations identified by Eco-tourism Directorate, according to the statistics, Thenmala and Periyar Tiger Reserve rank best in terms of tourist arrivals. So they have been selected for the study.

2.3 Objectives of the Study

- To understand the relationship between REL and tourist grievances.
- The study is basically a fact finding one that concentrates on improving the service quality and to understand the effect of REL experiment on behavioural science knowledge and to understand whether local tourist guides have a positive outlook towards their jobs.

2.4 Hypotheses of the Study

The hypotheses evolved for the present study are the following.

- There is no relationship between REL and tourist grievances.
- There is no relationship between REL and behavioural science knowledge of local tourist guides.

2.5 Research Methodology

The study is explorative in nature and hence is designed as a hypothesis testing one. Two kinds of hypothesis testing designs are introduced.

1. Before-and-after without control design: In this design a single test group is selected and the dependent variable is measured before the introduction of REL. The REL programme is then introduced and the dependent variable is measured again after the REL programme has been introduced. The effect of the treatment would be equal to the level of phenomenon after the REL programme minus the level of phenomenon before the REL programme.
2. Before-and-after with control design: In this design two groups are selected and the dependent variable is measured in both the groups for an identical time period before the introduction of REL. The programme is then introduced into the test group only, and the dependent variable is measured in both for an identical time-period after the introduction of the REL. The REL effect is determined by subtracting the change in the dependent variable in the control group from the change in the dependent variable in test group.

Several issues relating to the main aspects of the study were discussed in detail with experts, researchers and other eminent personalities in the field of tourism to get an insight into the subject prior to the collection of data

2.6 Sources of Data

Both primary and secondary sources of data are collected for this study.

2.7 Primary Data

The primary data is collected through interview methods from respondents with the help of a 'structured interview schedule' before and after the introduction of REL programme.

2.8 Secondary Data

At the explorative stage of the study, a detailed survey of literature has been undertaken in order to be familiarized with the various aspects of eco-tourism. Tourism is an area in which most of the financial and business experts and government agencies are actively interested. They normally conduct studies and publish articles about the tourism trends and the impacts of tourism in our economy. To evolve an appropriate methodology for the study and to formulate a conceptual framework for the study, the secondary data has been immensely helpful. For these purposes, various secondary sources like books and periodicals, research articles, seminar reports, newspapers, study reports of expert committees, departmental publications, plan documents, unpublished dissertations, etc have been surveyed. A careful survey of literature helped the researcher to collect and synthesize prior studies and to discover the important variables relevant to the problem.

2.9 Universe of the Study

Periyar Tiger Reserve and Thenmala have been selected for this study as they have been developed to the full potential according to the information and statistics available from Eco-tourism Directorate of Kerala.

As it is not possible to put the entire organisation for experiment, a part of the organisation has been selected. Here the entire populations of local guides in both the areas have been put for experiments. Eventhough, the focus group is local guides in order to conform to the basic definition of REL; the study is an organisation wide-effort. As the researcher is aware of interdependencies, interrelatedness, multiple causes and multiple effects, even though individuals are the instruments of change, not individuals, the total system is the target of change. Organisation Development is

applied as a Process That Focuses on Organisational Culture, Processes and Structure Utilising a Total System Perspective.

2.10 Collection of Data

The data has been collected by conducting interviews with the samples selected for the study. Multiple choice questions, open-end questions, rankings by the respondents and a five point scale developed by the researcher especially for this in conformity with statistical methods and principles are used wherever necessary

2.11 Analysis of the Data

The collected primary data are statistically processed, classified and tabulated by using appropriate methods. Since the sample size is small, tables, diagrams and statistical results are derived with the help of the computer software called SPSS (Statistical Packages for Social Sciences)

2.12 Limitations of the Study

Since the study is an individual effort, the investigator would like to point out some unavoidable limitations, which have been entered into the study. They are the following.

REL is a highly interdisciplinary, eclectic field. It has been built from theory, research and practice in social psychology, adult education, community development, general systems theory, family group therapy, anthropology, philosophy, counseling, psychiatry, general management, social work, human resource management, large conference management and other fields. It was not easy to incorporate methodologies from all the disciplines and put into experiment

Problems with internal validity such as whether REL interventions solely contributed change in the Eco-tourism destination or not is not easily gaugable. Because destinations cannot be singled out for experiments. Moreover extraneous factors like climate change can overrule the entire eco-tourism activities.

This research is also not free from problems which are inherent with attitude measurement.

2.13 Conceptual and Operational Definitions

There are some conceptual and operational definitions in the study when the research progresses. For instances

Behaviour Modification: It is a programme where managers identify performance related employee behaviours in tourism destinations and then implement an intervention strategy to strengthen desirable performance behaviours and weaken undesirable behaviours.

Encounter Groups: Encounter groups aim to provide participants with intense experiences to help them in their ways of interacting with tourists, their styles of self presentation, their values, etc.

Role playing: Role playing develops certain competencies such as perceiving the feelings and ideas of tourists, learning skill of relating a situation, gaining better insight into inter-personal relations.

Administering Instruments: These instruments increase self-awareness and interpersonal effectiveness through feedback among local people who act as tourist guides.

CHAPTER 3: DATA ANALYSIS-REL TEST PROCESS

3.1 Retrospective Experiential Learning (REL)

REL is a relatively permanent change in behaviour that occurs as a result of reproducing one's best previous experiences. Here the experiment has been done at Thenmala and PTR regarding Customer Relations Management. Guides have been asked to recollect their experiences about the following. Left a tourist in a good frame of mind or explained something to the tourist in a way that he or she understood and the guide learned something unexpectedly. The chances are that the guides are aware of some of the elements of their strategies but equally the chances are that there are some crucial bits of which the guides have no conscious knowledge. Guides have been asked to recollect their words and style of communication such as gestures, postures, composure, disposition, overall body language and eye contact and ultimately approach at that point of time. They have been asked to document it and go through it. The idea was to make it standardised rather than happening it erratically. Objective of this experiment was to help one live within one's potential rather than imposing a strategy from outside. Retrospective Experiential Learning (REL) is a learning instrument developed by the researcher.

Extended Summary

Objectives of the Experiment

1. To understand the relationship between REL and tourist complaints
2. To understand the relationship between REL and economic benefits of local tourist guides.
3. To understand the viability of Variable Analysis Model of OD.

Hypotheses of the Experiment

1. There is no relationship between REL and tourist complaints.
2. There is no relationship between REL and economic benefits of local tourist guides.
3. Dependent Variable (Behaviour Modification of Local Tourist Guides) is negatively correlated with Independent Variable (Problems in the Local Tourist Guides' environment)

Table 3.1 Results of Retrospective Experiential Learning at Thenmala

Before REL		After REL	
Oct-Dec 18	2.6		
Jan-Mar 19	2.7		
Apr-June 19	2.5		
Jul-Sept19		0.4	

Table 3.2 Results of Retrospective Experiential Learning at PTR

Percentage of Customer Complaints at PTR		After REL
Before REL		
Oct-Dec 18	2.6	
Jan-Mar19	2.9	
Apr-June 19	2.8	
Jul-Sept19		0.4

Conclusion: It has been found that both in PTR and in Thenmala after the application of Retrospective Experiential Learning, percentages of customer complaints have come down below one percent. It shows that REL can produce results.

Table 3.3 Customer satisfaction-based Incentive Earnings Increased for Guides

Period	Average Incentive Earnings(Rs) at PTR
Oct 17-Nov 17	43
Dec 17-Jan 18	55
Feb 18-Mar 18	65
Apr 18-May18	70
Jun 18-Jul 18	75
Aug 18- Sep 18	102

From the table, it can be inferred that at the beginning of OD programme, average incentives earned by the local tourist guides was Rs.43, later on when the OD programme got implemented through different phases, there is a gradual improvement in the average incentives earned by the tourist guides. At the end of the OD programme, it has come up to Rs 102. The fact is still corroborated by less number of customer complaints through REL. Better customer satisfaction resulted in better financial incentives from the part of tourists.

Figure 7.1 Average Earnings at PTR

Table 3.4 Customer satisfaction-based Incentive Earnings Increased for Guides

Period	Average Incentive Earnings(Rs) at Thenmala
Oct 17-Nov 17	55
Dec 17-Jan 18	60
Feb 18-Mar 18	60
Apr 18-May 18	70
Jun 18-Jul 18	70
Aug 18- Sep 18	100

Figure 7.2 Average Earnings at Thenmala

The succeeding charts after the tables, show that tourists' level of satisfaction increased and this in turn had resulted in better earnings for the guides in both the destinations. Hence the research hypothesis about economic status does not stand. As the entire group of tourist guides has been surveyed, there is no room for standard error or sampling error. So the graphical representation is sufficient to explain the hypothesis about economic status of local tourist guides.

Future Action Implication of the Research Hypothesis

Tourism providers today define eco-tourism to their convenience and advantage. A solar heating system, water recycling unit or use of paper bags is good enough for an hotelier to lay claim to the eco-tourism label. This is what accreditation process at national and international levels tend to facilitate in the form of eco-labelling. Still the stakeholders in tourism industry struggle to segregate eco-tourism and eco-friendly tourism ("Eco Labelling", 2012). However, they evade putting into practice certain broadly evolved norms of eco-tourism. This contradiction will

continue as long as tourism remains in the ambit of profit making and forgets that eco-tourism is based on principles of participation, consultation and sharing of benefits among all stakeholders, especially the local communities (**local tourist guides**) on whose resources eco-tourism thrives.

It is the duty of authorities to see to it that indigenous people and local communities agree to initiating tourism in their lands, and have direct participation in the planning, implementation, regulation and monitoring of tourism activities that affect them. **Most importantly, unless an attractive benefit-sharing mechanism is put in place based on customer satisfaction, tourism can never rebound to their interest.** Or else indigenous people and local communities will continue to be mere cogs in the wheel of this cash rich industry. **The above research hypothesis was tested based on indirect financial incentives earned by the local tourist guides from tourists.**

Feasibility of Variable Analysis Model

There are different approaches to Change Management. However, all models of Change Management is concerned with behaviour modification of employees and hence to improve their efficiency and that of the organisation. Here the researcher has developed **Variable Analysis Model of Change Management**. The concept is very simple if any problem of the employee in his internal or external environment (Independent Variable) gets sorted out; it would result in behaviour modification (Dependent Variable) of the employee. Here when the tourist service quality problems got sorted out through REL, it resulted in behaviour modification of the local tourist guides. Behaviour modification led to lower level of tourist complaints and greater economic benefits for the local tourist guides. When REL was applied, tourist complaints came down to below one percent in Thenmala and PTR. In both the

destinations, there is a significant improvement in local tourist guides' economic benefits after the introduction of REL. Less complaints from the part of tourists, obviously show greater customer satisfaction. When the customer satisfaction levels of tourists improved considerably, it resulted in generous tips from their part. It has been empirically proved that behaviour modification of local tourist guides' is negatively correlated with problems in their working environment. The model got applied through **IDRIA Design**, where I is the independent variable (customer problems in the tourism environment), D is the dependent variable (behaviour modification of tourist guides) and RIA is the remedial intervention (Retrospective Experiential Learning) to sort out customer complaints.

Verifiability of Experiment Hypotheses

From the tabular data, it can be inferred that there is relationship between customer complaints and REL. After the application of REL, customer complaints have come down to below one percent.

Obviously, less complaints from customers resulted in greater economic benefits as tabulated in tables . Because it resulted in generous tips from tourists.

As elaborated above, Variable Analysis Model is a working model in this context. Here the service quality problems are the independent variable. When it got sorted out through REL, it resulted in behaviour modification of local tourist guides (Dependent Variable).

How REL Was Practised

As Retrospective Experiential Learning is used for behaviour modification, it has been termed as REB Mod (Retrospective Experiential Behaviour Modification). The typical REB Mod. Programme follows a six step problem solving model.

REB Mod.

1. Recollect an incident in which one tourist has been left with complete satisfaction and the guide learned something accidentally.
2. Recollect the behavioural cues on that occasion, including gestures, postures, eye contacts and overall body language and wordings.
3. Document the said behavioural cues and wordings.
4. Take the pledge that it does not get revealed to other guides in order to avoid duplication and hence to maintain uniqueness.
5. Make enough rehearsals to get it into the groove.
6. Practice it in day to day guiding.

Step 1

Each and every guide was directed to make an honest retrospection into one's guiding interaction after a week's activities. This is very important because they are the interaction frontline personnel. The guides have to take out one incident of guiding that stands out from the rest and has to recollect the entire incident from the beginning to the end.

Step 2

The guides have to individually document the behavioural cues and wording without disclosing the same to their peers.

Step 3

They are directed to take the pledge regarding the maintenance of confidentiality about what they had learned accidentally.

Step 4

Guides are directed to perform at least five rehearsals about what they have learnt unexpectedly so that they can reproduce the behavioural cues and wordings as and when the situation demands. Ultimately, they are directed to document what they

have learnt through observation, experiments, impromptu, feedback and through encountering real world problems.

Step 5

Guides are directed to go through it before embarking their routine guiding and to practice it in their day-to-day guiding.

As the principles of uniqueness and non-duplication are relevant here, theories of knowledge management and knowledge sharing do not inspire confidence. In simple words, REL is all about exploring one's unknown potential and hidden talents and hence to reinforce the same and make it routine so that it results in behaviour modification.

3.2 Concentrated vs Differentiated Strategy of REL

Through Human Resource Committees at PTR and Thenmala, the researcher sought the possibility of exploring a concentrated strategy for implementing REL at PTR and Thenmala on an eight-dimensional scale of ten points each. The dimensions and their meanings are given below.

Tourism Performance- primary tourism product characteristics like the nature of eco-tourism activities.

Features- additional benefits to the tourists

Conformance-meeting eco-tourism industry standards

Service- redressing customer complaints

Response- interpersonal behaviour

Aesthetics- manifestation of eco-tourism products

Brand Equity- impression about the destination or its ranking

Customer Satisfaction- Keeping the tourist in delights and makes him loyal.

REL characteristics were tested by 16 tourist members from Thenmala and PTR on the said set of scale items and the scale is ordinal. The hypothesis, that there is no difference in REL Characteristics in two destinations has been tested at 5% level of significance by Wilcoxon matched- pairs signed rank test. tourist members at PTR and Thenmala have been brought together on a common platform. The researcher has given them room to discuss REL characteristics as regards with both the destinations. Each member rated REL characteristics in both the destinations based on his own perceptions. The researcher had taken down the minutes of the lively discussions. The findings of the discussions are elaborated under eight different themes but possibly overlapping ones. ANOVA test has been done at the end of the brainstorming sessions.

Table 3.5 Scores of REL Characteristics

SL No. of HRC Members	Destinations	
	Thenmala	PTR
1	73	51
2	43	41
3	47	43
4	53	41
5	58	47
6	47	32
7	52	24
8	58	58
9	38	43
10	61	53
11	56	52
12	56	57
13	34	44
14	55	57
15	65	40
16	75	68

The researcher composed the following hypothesis :

Null Hypothesis: There is not any change amongst the perceived REL elements of two destinations.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a change amongst the perceived REL elements of two destinations.

Analytical Results: After dropping the pair number 8 (difference is zero), there are only 15 observations. As the test is two- tailed, the tabled value at five percentage level of risk is 25, while the calculated value is 18.5. As the calculated value is not as much of the tabled value, the null hypothesis does not stand and we conclude that there is variance amongst the perceived REL elements of the two destinations. Therefore, it can be concluded that concentrated REL strategy is not applicable for the two destinations.

3.3 ANOVA TEST- TO TEST THE LIKELIHOOD OF SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE FROM TOURISTS :

The researcher wanted to know whether there is any significant difference as regards with accepting tourist guides between the tourists from different places after implementing REL. Because during the discussions domestic tourists showed greater resistance than their foreign counter parts. Tourists were assessed on a five-dimensional scale (each dimension is having ten points) on weekly basis for a period of four consecutive weeks. The researcher assessed tourists from different levels based on openness to new communication, sharing new thoughts, encouraging new thoughts, accepting new thoughts and implementing new thoughts.

Table 3.6: Weekly Likelihood of Social Acceptance from Tourists

Week	Different Supervisory Levels		
	Local	National	Foreign
First	30	25	25
Second	35	25	20
Third	15	15	15
Fourth	40	35	20

The researcher composed the following hypotheses

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between the positions of supervisors in organisational hierarchy and likelihood of implementing new ideas.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is relationship between the positions of supervisors in organisational hierarchy and likelihood of implementing new ideas.

The researcher composed the following hypotheses

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between the positions of supervisors in organisational hierarchy and likelihood of implementing new ideas.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is relationship between the positions of supervisors in organisational hierarchy and likelihood of implementing new ideas.

Table 3.7 Analysis of Variance Table for One-factor ANOVA Test

Source of Variation	Sum of Square (SS)	Degrees of freedom (d.f)	Mean Square (MS)-SS/d.f	F-ratio	F-critical value
Between samples	200	2	100	100/66.6	4.26 (for 2,9 d.f)
Within samples	600	9	66.6	=1.50	
Total	800	11			

Analytical Results

The calculated F value is less than the critical F value ($1.50 < 4.26$). Thus, we accept the null hypothesis that there is no difference in different supervisory positions as regards with implementing new ideas. During the discussions, the lower level supervisors showed resistance because of their inability to comprehend new ideas, not because of the fact that it is not amenable to them. After all lower level supervisors are not resistant to implementing new ideas, provided things are clear to them. Management experts no longer automatically assume that using intuition to make decisions is irrational or ineffective (Agor,1986)[24]. Here the supervisors who are assessed in connection with implementing new ideas told that they would prefer intuitive, imaginative, creative, participative and idea generating environment to work with rather than a rigid bureaucratic environment.

3.4 STATUS QUO OF BEHAVIOURAL SCIENCE APTITUDE:

Before the identification of guiding problems and remedial interventions, the researcher wanted to know the behavioural science aptitude of the local tourist guides. To create an informal and collaborative culture, the researcher had conducted a

descriptive behavioural science test in the regional language based on four parameters- Knowledge, Skills, Attitudes and Values and the scores are tabulated below.

First of all, Chi-square test has been conducted to analyse whether the behavioural science knowledge of local tourist guides is the same in Thenmala as well as in Periyar Tiger Reserve. Even though there are 23 local guides in Periyar Tiger Reserve, 20 work on regular terms. Regarding the 31 local guides in Thenmala, one person was erratic. So, he has been left out.

Table 3.8 Marks Obtained in Behavioural Science Test.

Marks Obtained in Behavioural Science Test	Eco-tourism Destinations		Total
	Thenmala	Periyar Tiger Reserve	
More than 50%	17	18	35
Less than 50%	3	12	15
Total	20	30	50

The researcher composed the following hypotheses

Null hypothesis: Guides in both the destinations are having same competency.

Alternative hypothesis: Competency levels are different in different locations.

The researcher wanted to know whether it could be inferred that local guides who performed poorly in behavioural science test are relatively more in Periyar Tiger Reserve than in Thenmala. Chi-square test has been applied in order to find out the same.

Analytical Results of Behavioural Science Test

The table generates Pearson Chi-square value-3.571 at 5 % level of significance and at one degree of freedom. The same value is 2.480 after the continuity correction. In both the cases, the value of significance is above .05. It shows that the null hypothesis stands. We can conclude that there is no difference so far as behavioural science awareness in Thenmala and Periyar Tiger Reserve. That is levels of competency of local guides remain the same at both sites. Here, Yates correction was done since one cell value is below 5.

As the scores in both the destination rank low in terms of job characteristics inventory, it do not lead to desirable personal and work outcomes. In order to make further analysis, the researcher has decided to go deeper into the problem. That is why Motivational Performance Scores (MPS) have been calculated.

The MPS is calculated as follows:

$$\text{MPS} = \frac{\text{Skill variety} + \text{Task identity} + \text{Task significance}}{3} \times \text{Autonomy} \times \text{Feedback}$$

Note. Adapted from Study Material Ignou,MS-10,2004 [25]

Table 3.9 MPS scores at Thenmala.

SL No.	Scores of Guides	SL No.	Scores of Guides	SL No.	Scores of Guides
1	84	11	140	21	14
2	112	12	7	22	84
3	112	13	7	23	84
4	140	14	21	24	140
5	140	15	14	25	140
6	112	16	28	26	42
7	84	17	63	27	7
8	84	18	63	28	105
9	63	19	63	29	140
10	63	20	21	30	140

The maximum MPS score is 1000. However, the achievement is far below from the peak score. It shows that many motivational factors have to be injected as remedial interventions.

Table 4.10 MPS scores at PTR

SL No.	Scores of Guides	SL No.	Scores of Guides
1	84	11	7
2	105	12	105
3	63	13	105
4	63	14	126
5	30	15	14
6	112	16	84
7	84	17	63
8	84	18	63
9	126	19	126
10	21	20	7

The entire population of twenty tourist guides in PTR and the entire population of thirty tourist guides in Thenmala have been tested with characteristics of MPS and Job Characteristic Inventory.

Here also the achievement is far below the maximum score. It is not a good sign and the researcher put serious attention over this matter. The researcher decided to take steps to improve the internal motivation of local tourist guides.

3.5 ASSESSING THE COMPETENCY OF GUIDES AFTER REL AND SURVEY FEEDBACK INTERVENTIONS :

The researcher himself had tested the behavioural science awareness of local guides after putting them into REL and survey feedback interventions.

Table 3.11 Marks Obtained in Performance Assessment Test

Marks Obtained	Periyar Tiger Reserve	Thenmala	Total
More than 50%	5	25	30
Less than 50%	15	5	20
Total	20	30	50

The null hypothesis has been taken in such a way that there is no difference in the performance of local guides in PTR and Thenmala. The researcher had worked out chi-square value and the value is found to be 17. As it is pretty larger than the theoretical value, we can statistically conclude that there is a difference so far as performance in training interventions in Thenmala and Periyar Tiger Reserve. That is levels of competency of local guides are now different at both the sites. This is supported by the fact that the interventions that are applied at Thenmala are more consistent because along with REL survey feedback has been applied in Thenmala. It shows that OD Interventions including survey feedback paid dividends. Because the researcher depended on survey feedback along with REL at Thenmala.

After experimenting with different interventions, the researcher has adopted the following model to assess the impact of team building that occurred through various interventions. Team building is part of REL and survey feedback interventions and team building itself is an intervention.

The Approach-To -Action Prototype (Schiffman, Leon G Kanuk & Leslie Lazar,1997) [26]) is directed towards a person's approach towards working with an object, not the approach towards the object. For instance, some people may like an organisation from different perspectives, at the same time they do not want to work with that organisation for some other reasons.

The attitude-towards-behaviour model is portrayed through the ensuing model equation.

$$\text{Approach (beh)} = \sum_{i=1}^n b_i e_i$$

In the equation b_i denotes sticking on with a wildlife sanctuary would bring economic benefits; e_i is the evaluation of the i th outcome. (favourableness of getting economic benefits) and \sum indicates the products getting added together.

An illustration of how Approach-To-Action calculated

It has been calculated concerning guides' willingness to stick on with Periyar Tiger Reserve and Thenmala. The average score is +2.8 for Periyar Tiger Reserve and the same for Thenmala is +2.9. It shows that local guides have a positive approach towards the Eco-tourism destinations

Secondary Method of Approach-To-Action (beh) :

Instances of interactive beliefs (b_j): Sticking on with Periyar Tiger Reserve is

Very likely [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very unlikely to give me a definite career.

Sticking on with Periyar Tiger Reserve is

Very likely [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very unlikely to give me economic benefits Sticking on with Periyar Tiger Reserve is

Very likely [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very unlikely to give me social benefits

Sticking on with Periyar Tiger Reserve is

Very likely [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very unlikely to improve my knowledge regarding environment.

Sticking on with Periyar Tiger Reserve is

Very likely [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very unlikely to improve my knowledge regarding local culture.

Even though the above readings can show one aspect (sticking on with one destination) for different reasons, actually it tests the holistic approach or positive vibrancy in terms of the different needs of the local tourist guides.

The same methodology has been applied for both the destinations

Evaluative (ej) component might be measured as: Sticking on with a destination for a definite career path is

Very good [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very bad

Sticking on with a destination for economic benefits

Very good [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very bad

Sticking on with a destination for social benefits

Very good [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very bad

Sticking on with a destination for improving environmental awareness

Very good [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very bad

Sticking on with a destination for improving the knowledge regarding local culture

Very good [+3] [+2] [+1] [0] [-1] [-2] [-3] Very bad

Survey Research

The researcher conducted in-depth interview using the above given questionnaire. Twenty guides from Periyar Tiger Reserve and another thirty guides from Thenmala were interviewed.

Table 3.12 Hypothetical Findings for the Attitude-Towards-Behaviour Analysis for eco-tourism destinations(Average Results)

Attitude	Evaluation (e _j)	Beliefs (b _i)			
		Thenmala		Periyar Tiger Reserve	
		b	be	b	be
Definite Career Path	+3	+1	+3	+2	+6
Economic Benefits	+3	+1	+3	+1	+3
Social Benefits	+1	+3	+3	+3	+3
Environmental Benefits	+2	+1	+2	+3	+6
Cultural Benefits	+2	+2	+4	+3	+6
Total $\sum b_i e_i$			+15		+24

Comments

The definite career path and the economic benefits are the two most important attributes (each with a positive value of +3 values). The fact that social benefits received only a +1 value does not mean that it is unimportant, but rather that guides tended to assume that two destinations were equally important.

Periyar Tiger Reserve was assessed positively with a total score of +24 followed by Thenmala with a total score of +15. The results show that the guides have a positive outlook (**Attitude**) towards destinations. That results in guides sticking on with destinations (**Behaviour**) for perceived benefits.

The above comments represent just some of the team development thoughts that flow from research findings, and illustrate the types of insights possible from such analyses. . Retrospective Experiential Learning is a behaviour science intervention designed by the investigator intended to improve the day to day guiding activities in ecotourism destinations [27]. Ultimately it will boost up the eclectic theories of economics by concentrating on the baselines of Eclectic Theories like making the business international through consultancy ownership and customising the product for the locational needs.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 FINDINGS

One of the main methods to distinguish an ecotourism endpoint is to provide reliably great excellence facility than other kinds of tourism. The main factor is to come across or outdo the target travellers' service excellence outlooks. Consumer gratification is one of the central drives of an excellence organisation scheme (Cochran & Craig, 2001) [28]. This brain storming session was aimed at improving the tourist satisfaction and the tourist guides' motivation levels. Client devotion can be continued only by upholding a positive assessment when equated with other players

The behaviour science proficiency has been tested in both the destinations before the application of REL and other interventions; it has been found that proficiency is same in both the destinations. But after the application of REL and other robust intervention like survey feedback it has been found that behavioural science proficiencies are different in both the locations. At the beginning Motivational Performance Scores were low. But after a series of structured interventions like REL and Survey feedback, it got corroborated that local tourist guides have got a positive outlook towards their destinations that prompt them to carry on their jobs in both the destinations.

At the beginning of the study, Pearson Chi-square value after continuity correction was only 2.480 and it leads to the inference that behavioural science proficiency of local tourist guides are more or less same in both the destinations. After the application of interventions like REL and survey feedback, the nonparametric test Chi-square test has been done again and the computed value 17 is much above than the theoretical value. It leads to the conclusion of turning down the null hypothesis and accepting the inference that behavioural science knowledge is different in both the destinations. In both the destinations it has been found that the Motivational

Performance Scores are much below than the maximum value 1000. So, after the introduction of the developed learning intervention REL and the existing intervention Survey feedback, it has been found that local tribal tourist guides have a positive attitude towards sticking on with tourist destinations for expected paybacks. The figures are +24 at PTR and +15 at Thenmala respectively. This result is commendable because earlier the motivational performance scores were nowhere near the maximum. Ultimately it can be inferred that structured interventions can bring about positive mind sets.

4.2 IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS & FUTURE SCOPE :

Still, the stakeholders in the tourism industry struggle to segregate eco-tourism and ecofriendly tourism. This contradiction will continue as long as tourism remains in the ambit of profit making and forgets that eco-tourism is nature based on the support of the local populace. Further research can be concentrated on applying REL to cater to the different needs of eco-tourists such as appreciating and conserving nature, acquiring knowledge on nature etc. It's a subtle and minute research area with the greater focus on differentiated needs of the tourists.

Through the REL interventions and survey feedback, it has been found that guides have got a positive vibe towards both destinations and their behaviour science knowledge is different after the application of interventions like REL and survey feedback. Need-based training and need-based products are the need of the hour. Now the question is whether the guiding style can be differentiated based on the differentiated needs of the tourists. It is a matter of providing need-based REL interventions. But still, a lot of research needs to be done to segment the ecotourism products and tourists. Because they are broadly categorised in the segment of Eco

tourists. Further research can be done on the impact of positive mind sets on productivity and better service quality.

4.3 BENEFITS FROM THE STUDY

i) Researcher

It would help the researcher to partially fulfil the requirements for the award of Post Doctoral Fellow.

ii) Tourists

Tourists experience better sense of belonging and inner fulfilment during the REL implementation period.

iii) Tourist Guides

Tourist guides experienced participative management and efficiency enhancing interpersonal behaviour. Economic status and social status of guides improved during the REL implementation period.

iv) Organisation

Organisation has been converted as a learning organisation during the REL implementation period. Problems as regards with structural, procedural, behavioural, cultural and motivational have been sorted out.

4.4 CONCLUSION:

Positive vibes always contribute to better customer satisfaction. Here in this study REL and Survey feedback interventions resulted in a better attitude towards the behaviour model. As it has produced better results in destinations like Thenmala and PTR, it's' high time to take it to other ecotourism destinations across the globe which requires consultancy services as well as manpower supports. Internationalisation of ecotourism operations through better services can bring benefits to ecotourism operators at home and its foreign counterparts. As ecotourism follows stringent quality

parameters, development potential is limited in particular destinations, the next option is to move it across the globe so that the business potential keeps on growing. Once internationalisation happens, it will foster the Eclectic Theories of Economics. As the emphasis is on intergroup and intragroup dynamics with the assistance of structured activities like Retrospective Experiential Learning it results in better interrelations and social capital.

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Annexure-I

**BEHAVIORAL COMPONENTS OF
GUIDES' INDIVIDUAL PERFORMANCE**

Name of the Guide:

Name of the Immediate Supervisor:

Assessment Scale

No	Behavioural Components	1	2	3	4	5
A	KNOWLEDGE					
1	General knowledge of the field / area / sector					
2	Specific knowledge in a sub field/ area/sector					
3	Specific knowledge related to operational aspects					
4	Knowledge about the relationship between the field/ area /sector/ work and social environment					
5	Knowledge about the relationship between the field/ area /sector/ work and personal development					
6	Knowledge about stakeholders/ clients/ and client expectations					
7	Knowledge about employer/boss expectation					
8	Knowledge about group dynamics in the work organisation					
9	Knowledge about efficiency methods					
10	Knowledge about basic human psychology/ human behaviour					
B	SKILLS					
1	Skills in handling the job allotted					
2	Skills in Communication					
3	Skills in Public Relations					
4	Skills in motivating oneself//team members					
5	Skills in participation management / team building					
6	Skills in time management					
7	Skills in client oriented thinking					
8	Skills in giving professional leadership					
9	Skills in interpersonal relationship					
10	Skills in Problem Solving					

C	ATTITUDES				
1	Being basically positive in life				
2	Motivation for excellence in work and service				
3	Motivation for professional leadership				
4	Motivation for social leadership in the place of work				
5	Strong and abiding desire for continuous development				
6	Optimism as a basic driving force				
7	Being pleasant in behaviour towards others				
8	Fairness to clients, colleagues, superiors				
9	Sense of responsibility and accountability				
10	Basic concern for others in the work place				
D	VALUES				
1	Commitment To Moral Or Ethical Values Of The Society				
2	Treating job as something more than a mere means of income				
3	Acceptance of social obligations				
4	Acceptance of obligations to the stakeholders/ clients				
5	Acceptance of obligations to the organisations/employer				
6	Acceptance of obligations to the profession to which one belongs				
7	Acceptance of basic human values				
8	Acceptance of the moral aspects of means to be employed for getting results and rewards in life and in the organisation				
9	Giving priority for professional excellence				
10	Integrating personal goals with organisational goals				